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BRAND INNOVATIVENESS AND CONSUMERS' CHOICE FOR DECORATIVE PAINT IN THE SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of product innovation on consumers' choice for decorative paint, in the South East, Nigeria. The major objective of the study was to: ascertain the effect of brand innovativeness on consumers' choice of decorative paints. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire. The population was drawn from the contractors and painters operating in the three commercial cities in the three states chosen among the five states of southeast Nigeria. Due to the nature of the population, it could be described as being unknown and therefore a sample size of 384 was determined using the Zigmund formula which is suitable for an unknown population. The result of statistical analysis revealed that brand innovativeness has a significant effect on consumer choice. It was concluded that the study has filled the gap in the literature by providing the knowledge base that when brand innovativeness is improved for decorative paint; it increases consumer choice. It was therefore recommended among others that decorative paint companies should embark on product innovation initiatives in order to enlarge their loyal customer base.

KEYWORDS

Product innovation, Brand Innovativeness, Consumer Choice, Decorative Paints.

Introduction

The success of new product introduction in the marketplace is very critical for long term organizational performance. This is particularly so for industries in which firms utilize technologies for innovation, under the idea that they will be able to bring out new products using these technologies (Prins & Verhoef, 2007). For example, in Nigeria, paint companies invest heavily in product innovation in the decorative paint segment due to the fact that “decorative segment accounts for about 60% of total sales value” in the paint industry (Naijalink, 2014, p.16). This is a reflection of consumer choice of decorative paints in the Nigerian market.

Consumer choice which is an outcome of a consumer’s decision making process is regarded as one of the most important concepts in a rapidly changing business environment that is characterized by intense competitiveness, unprecedented level of technological change as well as an emerging sustainability issues. The unpredictable business environment is fueled by advances in globalization and the growing importance of the global consumer (Kaplan 2009). The choices that consumers make are very crucial to the marketing effectiveness of organizations. This is as a result of the fact that, it is the cumulative effect of consumer choice that determines the market share captured by each product in the competitive marketplace.

The essential feature of the marketplace in the 21st century are: high level of production, high level of natural resource use, unprecedented competitive pressure, high level of consumption, short life span of products, and high rate of technological change coupled with an emerging sustainability awareness. At the same time, consumers are responding to these economic conditions by demanding for more sophisticated products to satisfy their needs and desires as well as personalized attention and solutions to their problems.

The above-mentioned therefore, represent the several challenges that organizations need to grapple with, in order to achieve competitive advantage as well as building organizational resilience. To achieve this, firms need to embark on successful marketing innovation initiatives, in terms of new product designs, new product packaging, new promotional methods and new pricing tactics, (Wang & Ahmed 2004, p; OECD, 2005).

The issue of consumer choice for decorative paints has been of serious concern not only to decorative paint company management, but also to the institutional customers, households and the general public. Over the years, decorative paint industry has suffered tremendous set back as a result of unfriendly operating business environment including financial illiquidity and frustration by players in the industry due to inefficient regulatory practices (Owoeye, 2018; Aluko, 2017; Naijalink, 2014; Lami Ogar, 2017). For instance, despite the launching of “operation flush out” by Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) in 2015 which was aimed at tackling sub-standard, fake, adulterated, and counterfeit products in the country, the impact is yet to be felt in the decorative paint industry. A 2016 Data from the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) reveals that there are only about 68 registered paint producers in Nigeria that meet SON requirements (Owoeye, 2018). However, the decorative paint industry has witnessed innovation and technological advancement in the methods of production, as a result of stiff competition within the industry as paint companies are forced to put in their best to ensure they remain relevant and competitive in the market, (Ogar 2017; Naijalink 2014).

Empirical studies in the area of product innovation-consumer choice relationship in the decorative paint industry in Nigeria are very scanty due to limited research work in this aspect. As a result, there is a need to fill the knowledge gap in existing literature. One of the few studies done was in Egypt, where Alamand Faridi (as cited in Shanmugapriya &Pratheepa, 2014) examined the perception and expectation level of institutional consumers towards paint brands. In Nigeria, OlumuandIrefin (2016) studied the effect of e-marketing adoption and organizational performance in the Nigerian paint industry. In Nigeria also, Amueand Adiele, (2012) examined the effect of new product development on consumer innovative behaviour in the context of high-tech consumer durable goods in Port Harcourt.

As seen above, empirical evidence from innovation literature is not clear on the role brand innovativeness play in the product innovation – consumer choice relationship. No research seems to have yet investigated the relationship between brand innovativeness as a dimension of innovation and consumer choice in a B2B product marketing such as the decorative paint industry in Nigeria. This current study addresses this apparent gap in literature.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Conceptual review here entails the conceptualization of the study constructs, the different proponents and the philosophies behind them. The respective dimensions of the independent variable and the latent measures of the dependent variable are equally explained.

Consumer Choice

Consumer choice describes the decisions that consumers make in the marketplace with regard to products and services. In the study of consumer choice behaviour, marketers tend to examine how consumers decide which products to purchase or consume over time. The cumulative effect of choices made by consumers in the marketplace is what determines the market share captured by a product. With the consumer markets that are characterised by intensive competition, it becomes imperative that the quest to reinforce brand success becomes a challenging task for the organisational managers. It is the organisation's capacity to achieve or build strong brand equity that is a credible indicator of brand success in the marketplace. As rational beings, the consumers during their purchase decision making process tend to form their "decisions based on their perceptions of added values and unique offerings of a brand" (Hanaysha, 2016, p.35).

Consumer choices therefore, reflect values and preferences of the consumers. This means that because the consumer is a rational being, the market choices he makes is expected to have the highest utility for him among all other choice options available in the market. The implication being that it is the consumer that puts value on the product. Hence, the concept of brand equity is very important to organisations because it is an indicator of a firm's capability to influence consumer behaviour. This explain why Lassar, et al (as cited in Hanaysha, 2016, p.36) defined brand equity as "the ability to enhance customers' perceived value and desirability toward a brand through product and service offerings". To enhance the perception of value in product and service offerings, extant literature suggests that product innovation plays an important role by influencing consumer choice through brand preference. This explain why Zhang and Tang (2017) are of the view that in response to this market demand, the role of an enterprises is to improve consumer adoption intention of new products.

Brand Innovativeness

Shams, Alpert, and Brown (2015, p.1594) defined brand innovativeness as the “consumers perception of a brand’s track record of product innovations, degree of creativity, and potential for continued innovative activity in the future in a given market”. The concept is different from innovation orientation and innovation capability. Conceptually, it is also different from novelty. Wells, Campbell, Valacich and Featherman, (2010, p.818) describes novelty as, “the degree to which a user perceives an innovation to be a new and exciting alternative”.

Brand innovativeness describes the degree of innovativeness of a firm from the eye of the consumers. Eisingerich and Rubera (2010, p.66) provides the simplest definition of brand innovativeness as, “the extent to which consumers perceive brands as being able to provide new and useful solutions to their needs”. Put differently, the researchers are of the view that the concept of brand innovativeness describes the capability of brands/organizations to launch or produce innovative products considered to be new and capable of meeting the needs of the target market.

Theoretical Review

Many of the theories that concern product innovation and consumer choice have been developed by researchers in the past, and each of the theories emphasizes on one or the other aspects of innovation and how it affects consumer behavioral intentions and choice making in the marketplace. In this study, some of such theories are considered.

Roger’s Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT): The making of a new product by entrepreneurs demands an effective commercialization strategy which relies upon marketing management, to make clear strategic choices as regards the target market where the organization wishes to compete and the crafting of a marketing strategy that is capable of providing a differential strategy. The target market and the differential strategy define the product positioning strategy (Jobber, 2006). Rogers (as cited in Jobber, 2006) argues that understanding the diffusion of innovation process starts with the choice of a target market. While propounding the theory of diffusion of innovation model, the author attributed the rate of diffusion of new product in the marketplace to a combination of “product differences” and “peoples differences”. It is suggested that about 87 percent of the difference in the rate of diffusion of an innovation could be attributed to the following five product characteristics, described as Roger’s Five Factors: Relative advantage,; Compatibility; Complexity; Trialability; and observability.

Relative advantage describes the degree to which a product is perceived to be better than the old product it is replacing. Consequently, the new product is assumed or believed to possess better quality than the existing product in the market. From the marketing perspective therefore, the relative advantage of a new product is in relation to the product or service performance enhancement as perceived by the consumers. Compatibility describes “the extent to which an innovation is perceived as being consistent with the values, past experiences and needs of the potential adopters” (Addo, 2016). The implication being that the utility value of the product is just like the replaced product and as such the expectations of the consumers will still be met.

Complexity, describes the characteristic of an innovative product that is perceived as being difficult to understand or use. Immediately it is introduced into the market new product becomes difficult to use. Consequently, it is the consumers’ fear of the unknown as well as the initial mistakes usually

associated with new product use that compels people to always prefer to wait or avoid innovative products until they see other consumers use it or possibly see a demonstration of its usage. Trialability describes the degree to which an innovation could be experimented to a limited level. This explains the period of time during the introduction or testing period of an innovation after which a decision is taken on its acceptance or rejection by the market. Observability, describe the degree to which the results of an innovation are visible to others. What happens at this stage is that while people are using the product/service others (potential users) are looking from their respective positions admiringly or with suspicion. The next thing they do is to start making enquiries about the innovation concerning their experiences, expectations, challenges as well as their comments about the innovation.

The knowledge of the product differences gives the marketer the latitude to manage the diffusion process by taking advantage of the "people differences". In his classical theory, Rogers (as cited by Addo, 2016) categorized the potential adopters of innovation into five: innovators; early adopters, early majority, late majority and the laggards. Innovators are assumed to form 2.5% of the population and they are often venturesome, risk takers and prefer to be different. They have more money to spend. The next group is the Early Adopters who form 13.5% of the population and considered to be above average age, education and income. Their source of information is informal. Early majority make up 34% of the population which is the second category. The late majority represents 34% of the population and is skeptical of trying new products. They only adopt new product after observing majority of the population or organizations try the product. Often times they adopt new products as a result of social pressure and recommendations from family and friends or other members of the society. The last group is made up of the laggards who represent 16% of the population.

Easinwood and Beard (as cited in Jobber, 2006) argues that Rogers categorization is very useful in providing the basis for market segmentation for innovative products as well as target market selection. Following the same line of thought, Addo (2016) is of the view that the categorization can help a firm to focus its limited resources on the target market with potential for patronage and capable of providing the best return on investment.

The reason why this theory anchors this study is not farfetched. The diffusion of innovation theory propounded by Rogers provides explanation on how the characteristics of new products lend credibility to perceived product quality which acts as a clue to consumers, thereby enhancing the adoption of such new products. Also, the categorization of consumers by the diffusion of innovation theory (DIT) makes it possible for marketers to easily select a target market with which appropriate marketing strategy could be developed to enhance consumer choice through brand preference and subsequent purchase intention.

Empirical Review and Hypothesis Development

Brand Innovativeness and Consumer Choice

Innovativeness is described as one of the critical success factors which is recognized as part of organizational valuable asset. This is sequel to the fact that in the new millennium customers are looking for breakthrough products which are not only convenient and unique but also affordable at the same time (Koplan 2009). This explain why Cervellon (as cited in Ahmad, Omar, Munap& Rose 2018) is of the view that brand manager should endeavour to communicate brand personality using

brand elements such as logo, packaging materials as well as innovative practices with a view to signaling to the target market the rich brand association and brand values. The essence is to achieve brand loyalty, since brand innovativeness acts as a signal of quality and commitment on the part of organizations based on unique brand associations possessed by the brand (Kolpan 2009).

There are several empirical studies that investigated the relationship between brand innovativeness and consumer in various sectors (Sanayei, Shahin & Taherfar, 2013; Kunz, Schmitt & Meyer, 2011; Bart, Andrikatesh, Fateena & Urban, 2005; Payne & Lema, 2016; Khan & Khan 2012, Anyaeme Alimi & Ayanbimipe, 2005; Ebrahim, et al 2016; Jun, Park & Yeom, 2014; Nemati, Khan, & Iftikhar 2010; Olumu & Irehfin 2016).

Sanayei, Shahin and Taherfar (2013) investigated the effects of brand innovativeness on brand attitude with consumer innovativeness acting as a moderating variable. The descriptive study used the questionnaire as major instrument for data collection from Isfaham university students through random sampling procedure. The findings of the study indicate that brand innovativeness has positive effect on consumer attitude towards brands. Also consumer innovativeness moderates the relationship between brand innovativeness and consumer attitude positively. Consequently, the researchers are of the view that organizations invest more on innovativeness as part of brand association with a view to enhancing the level of the target markets attitude towards the brand.

Kunz, Schmitt, and Meyer (2011) investigated the effect of perceived firm innovativeness (brand innovativeness) on consumer satisfaction and consumer loyalty. The descriptive study was divided into qualitative and quantitative methods and was utilized to develop and validate the perceived firm innovativeness (PFI) scale. The population for the study was 216 customers in the mobile phone industry. The results generated through structural equation modeling showed that perceived firm innovativeness had significant positive effect on brand loyalty. However the effect was weaker for services than consumer goods. The authors made a call for a broad-based systematic management of organizations' innovativeness from the perspective of the consumers

Pappu and Quester (2016) examined the effect of brand innovativeness on brand loyalty with perceived product quality performing a mediating role. The descriptive study developed a model that was tested in two empirical studies for three global consumer electronics brands in two product categories. The questionnaire was the major instrument for data collection. The respondents were consumers met at a major shopping complex using a mall-intercept approach. The findings show that brand innovativeness has positive and significant relationship with brand loyalty. Also, the perceived product quality mediated the relationship between brand innovativeness and brand loyalty. The authors argued that without perceived product quality, it will be difficult for the firm to boost consumer intended loyalty through being innovative.

Chuah, et al (2016) in Malaysia investigated the effect of perceived firm marketing innovation on customer perceived value and customer loyalty in the mobile telecommunication industry. A self administered questionnaire was utilized in data collection from Generation Y (18-34 years old) customers of four main networks who subscribe to post-paid mobile plans. The findings showed that perceived firm marketing innovation had positive effect on functional value and monetary value, functional value, monetary value and emotional value in turn all had significant positive effect on customer loyalty. The authors argued that for mobile telecommunication service providers to create

superior customer value and therefore enlarge their loyal customer base, they need to embark on marketing innovation initiatives.

Baharun, Nikbin, Hashim and Awang (2016) investigated the effect of product innovation on brand preference with brand personality performing a mediating role. The quantitative research design used the questionnaire as the major instrument for data collection. Through sampling approach, data were collected from university students who were the chosen respondents who own and operate mobile telecommunication brands. The result of the data analysis shows that innovation in telecommunication products has significant positive relationship with brand preferences as well as with brand personality. The authors suggested that brand and marketing managers could enhance the success of their brand positioning strategies in the marketplace through the measurement of consumers' perception of product innovation and brand personality in the target market.

Mourad and Ahmed (2012) investigated the factors affecting the green brand preference in the telecom industry in an emerging innovative market of Egypt. The qualitative exploratory and quantitative research, studied 302 respondents who are telecom customers. The findings showed that the respondents who are consumers of telecom products said they were not aware of environmental promotions of the telecom operators neither did they recognize the meaning of environmental labels and slogans for their preferred brand. Another finding showed that green awareness had weak correlation with green brand preference. There was positive and strong correlation between green brand image, green awareness, green trust and green brand preference. The authors made a case for the commencement or adoption of green marketing principles in Egypt with a view to promoting green image, green satisfaction and green trust. In addition, educating the consumers on the importance of green activities was emphasized.

OlumuandIrehfin (2016) examined the effect of e-marketing adoption and performance in the Nigerian paints industry. The descriptive study utilized the questionnaire as the major instrument for data collection. The unit of analysis was paint manufacturing firms operating in South East, Nigeria, through purposeful sampling technique.

The findings showed that the adoption of e-marketing strategies had positive effect on sales growth, customer retention and investment. Also e-marketing adoption was found to be negatively related to market share and marketing staff. The authors argued that firms should intensify the utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) for marketing innovation with the objective of promoting sales thereby enhancing profitability.

Nemati, Khan, and Iftikhar (2010) investigated the effect of product innovation on customer satisfaction and brand loyalty in Pakistan. The descriptive study adopted the questionnaire as the major instrument for data collection. The respondents were mainly shopkeepers, university students and the general public making use of mobile phones and residing in Rawalpindi and Islamabad. The convenient sampling technique was used in administering the questionnaires. The result of the statistical analysis showed that innovation is positively correlated with customer satisfaction but had no impact on brand loyalty. The authors are of the view that economic conditions of the target market should also be considered when planning to introduce innovative products into the market.

From the foregoing we hypothesize that.

H1: Brand innovativeness has no significant effect on consumer choice.

Research Methodology

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. This design is considered appropriate because its focus was on people and their belief, opinion, attitude, motivation and behaviour (Osuala, 1993; Eboh, 2009). The purpose of survey research involved collection of data, discovering meaning in the data collected, so that facts and events could be better explained, interpreted and understood (Ezejelue, Ogwo&Nkamnebe 2010). It equally consists of gathering data from usually a large number of respondents, who themselves constitute a sample.

Area of the Study: The area of this study is delineated in two ways: the study was conducted in the South East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The proposed geographical area of coverage for the study was the coal city of Enugu, the commercial city of Aba in Abia state and the commercial city of Onitsha in Anambra state. These states were chosen due to convenience in accessibility of information and the fact that paint business activities and consumption seems to be high in these states judging by the high rate of building infrastructure going on by individuals, estate developers and government, the high concentration of paint manufacturing firms, some of which are registered with Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN) and paint markets in the area was a big factor considered in the choice process.

Secondly, given that the location of the paint companies, painters, house owners, contractors, staff of organizations, and government institutions are scattered across towns in these states, the attention of this study focused more on painters and contractors situated in the state capital and commercial nerve centers of each state as the unit of analysis.

Source of Data Collection: The primary source of data was responses generated from self administered questionnaires. The primary data was therefore the responses generated from institutional consumers (painters and contractors) of decorative paints. The study sample was targeted at building sites, contractors' offices and painter's meeting points in the selected three South Eastern cities of Nigeria.

Population: The population chosen for a particular study is the theoretical aggregation of study elements (Malhotra, 2007). For this study, the population chosen was the institutional customers of decorative paints. They were made up of building contractors and painters who operate in the cities of Onitsha, Enugu and Aba; three big cities in South East, Nigeria. Due to the nature of the population, it was described as an infinite population. To qualify as respondents, they must have been in the painting business for more than two years (2017- 2019).

Sample Size Determination: The required sample unit (n) of contractors and painters (observation unit) indicated above was determined by using Zigmund formula (1979,p.66) which is suitable for an unknown population.

The mathematical formula is given as follows

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Z = Statistic to be used at 5% level of significance at two tail test = 1.96

e = Allowable sampling error taken at 5% = 0.05

p = proportion of success in the population from pilot survey = 0.5

q = proportion of failure in the population from pilot survey = 0.5

n = sample size required

$$n = \frac{1.96 \times 1.96 \times 0.50 \times 0.50}{0.05 \times 0.05} = 384.16=384$$

Based on the computation above, a sample of 384 contractors and painters was required for this study.

Sampling Technique: Specifically, the computed sample was allocated to each of the cities in these proportion; Onitsha (152), Enugu metropolis (110) and Aba (122). Consequent on the above, the sample of 384 among the three cities as shown above was chosen from their entire population using the purposive or judgmental sampling which is a non-probability sampling technique. The questionnaire was administered to available contractors and painters.

Measurement Instrument and Questionnaire design: The major instrument for data collection was a well-structured questionnaire. A five-point Likert-type scale anchored by: Strongly Disagree [SD](1), Disagree [D](2), Agree [A](3), Agree fairly strongly(4) and Strongly Agree [SA](5) was used to represent the measurement items and to express the degree of agreement with the items or otherwise.

All the items were adapted from extant literature. Brand innovativeness's six items was measured using items adapted from Shams, et al (2015), while the three items used for customer satisfaction were adapted from Ragunathan and Irwin (2001).

Validity: A research instrument is said to be valid if it measures what it is expected to measure. For this study, the researcher will use both face and content validity methods. In achieving these, some copies of the instrument were given to research experts for validation. While the instrument was vetted and certified valid (face validity), it was also critically assessed by the supervisor at the University of Nigeria, Enugu campus to ensure that the content of the instrument measures what the overall study is all about (content validity). Corrections and adjustments were made to enrich the validity of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument: The extent to which the responses obtained through each of the items on the instrument is internally consistent or the extent of response reproducibility over a number of times the instrument is tested is described as the reliability of the data collection instrument. The response from the study was tested for reliability using the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient method. The result from the test gave a value of .737. This is an indication that the instrument is reliable and should be used for the main study.

Demographic Profile: The demographic profile of the respondents revealed the following: 64(18%) of the respondents were contractors, while 292(82%) of the respondents were painters. The implication is that most of the respondents were painters who are the actual users of the paints; 138(39%) of the respondents were in Onitsha, 102(29%) of them were in Enugu metropolis, while 116(32%) of the respondents were in Aba city; 53(15%) of the respondents were females, while 303(85%) of the respondents were males. This implies that majority of the respondents (contractors/painters) were males; 34(9%) of the respondents were less than 20 years of age, 85(24%) of them were between 20-29 years, 130(37%) of them were between 30-39 years, while 107(30%) of them were 40 years and above; 50(14%) of the respondents had SSCE as their highest educational qualification, 148(42%) of them had BSc/HND, 121(34%) of them had MSc/MBA, while 37(10%) of the respondents had PhD as their highest educational qualification. This implies that majority of the respondents are graduates with BSc/HND; 96(27%) of the respondents were single, while 260(73%) of the respondents were married.

Testing of Hypothesis

The hypothesis was tested statistically in this section using T-test associated to regression, Partial correlation, and ANOVA. The result of the statistical testing was used to either accept or reject the null hypothesis formulated at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀: Brand innovativeness has no significant effect on consumer choice.

Table 3: T-test associated with simple Regression on the relationship between Brand Innovativeness and Consumer Choice

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
1					
(Constant)	5.737	1.062		5.401	.000
Brand Innovativeness	.653	.071	.562	9.165	.000

Table 1 revealed that brand innovativeness is significantly related to consumer choice by 0.562. The t-test value 9.165 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, brand innovativeness has a significant effect on consumer choice.

Discussion of Findings and Implications

Brand Innovativeness and Consumer Choice

The findings revealed a significant relationship between brand innovativeness and consumer choice. This was validated by the fact that paint brand sets itself apart from the rest when it comes to decorative paints, paint brand launches new decorative paints and creates market trends all the time, paint brand is an innovative brand when it comes to decorative paints, with regard to decorative paints, this paint brand constantly generates new ideas, paint brand makes decorative paints with superior colours and paint brand has changed the market with its decorative paints.

Sanayei, Shahin and Taherfar (2013) investigated the effects of brand innovativeness on brand attitude with consumer innovativeness acting as a moderating variable. The findings of the study revealed that brand innovativeness has positive effect on consumer attitude towards brands. Also, consumer innovativeness moderates the relationship between brand innovativeness and consumer

attitude positively. This agrees with the findings of the present study. Similarly, Kunz, Schmitt and Meyer (2011) investigated the effect of perceived firm innovativeness (brand innovativeness) on consumer satisfaction and consumer loyalty. The results generated through structural equation modeling showed that perceived firm innovativeness had significant positive effect on brand loyalty.

This implies that brand manager of manufacturing companies should endeavour to communicate brand personality using brand elements such as logo, packaging materials as well as innovative practices with a view to signaling to the target market the rich brand association and brand values. The aim being to achieve brand loyalty, since brand innovativeness acts as a signal of quality and commitment on the part of organizations based on unique brand associations possessed by the brand.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study has filled the gap in literature by providing the knowledge base that when product innovation is improved for decorative paint; it increases consumer choice. Also, the research has proven that brand innovativeness, can increase consumer choice among customers of decorative paint. Furthermore, the level of awareness towards importance and benefits of word of mouth communication and consumer innovativeness will encourage patronage and loyalty among customers. Decorative paint companies should invest more on innovativeness as part of brand association with a view to enhancing the level of the target markets attitude towards the brand. Brand and marketing managers should enhance the success of their brand positioning strategies in the marketplace through the measurement of consumers' perception of product innovation and brand personality in the target market.

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